

2021

Sonali Bank Ltd.

Internship Report by Md. Jalal Uddin

[Performance Evaluation of Export, Import Business of Sonali Bank Limited]

Sonali Bank Limited is a Govt. owned bank with the number of highest branches spreading all over Bangladesh. It operates its export, import operations with different countries.

Department of Finance and Banking

University of Barishal

An Internship Report on

“Performance Evaluation of Export, Import Business of Sonali Bank Limited”

Submitted to:

Md. Mahtab Uddin
Chairman,
BBA (Hon's), 4th Year Examination Committee-2019
Department of Finance & Banking,
University of Barishal.

Supervised by:

Rabeya Sultana Lata
Assistant Professor,
Department of Finance & Banking,
University of Barishal.

Prepared by:

Md. Jalal Uddin
Exam Roll: FIN016/8
ID No: 16FIN026
Session:2018-2019(A:S:2015-2016)
Department of Finance & Banking,
University of Barishal.

Date of Submission: 31st March, 2021

Letter of Transmittal

31st March, 2021

Rabeya Sultana Lata
Assistant Professor,
Department of Finance & Banking,
University of Barishal.

Subject: Submission of Internship Report on “*Performance Evaluation of Export, Import Business of Sonali Bank Limited*”

Dear Mam,

With due respect and humble submission I beg to state that it is a matter of great pleasure and honor for me to submit my internship report on “*Performance Evaluation of Export, Import Business of Sonali Bank Limited*” under your guideline. For preparing this report I have tried to follow your guideline. I have given my honest efforts to the study relevant materials, documents, the direct observed operations performed in “*Sonali Bank Limited, Chawkbazar Branch, Barishal*” and evaluate relevant record for preparation of the report. Within limited time, I have to make this report as extensive as possible.

Therefore, I will be highly encouraged and would remain grateful if you authorize the report.

Yours Sincerely

Md. Jalal Uddin

Md. Jalal Uddin
Exam Roll: FIN016/8
ID No: 16FIN026
Session: 2018-2019 (Admission Session: 2015-2016)
Department of Finance and Banking, University of Barishal.

CERTIFICATE OF SUPERVISOR

This is certified that, Md. Jalal Uddin, Exam ID No : FIN 016/8, Registration No : 161-026-16, Academic Session: 2015-16, is a regular student of 8th Semester (Final Semester) of BBA honors, Department of Finance and Banking, University of Barishal. He has completed an internship program on “Performance Evaluation of Export, Import Business of Sonali Bank Limited” Under my supervision which is fulfillment of partial requirement of obtaining BBA honors.

I wish his success in all his future endeavors.

Rabeya Sultana Lata
Assistant Professor
Department of Finance and Banking
University of Barishal

Letter of Acceptance

সোনালী ব্যাংক লিমিটেড
Sonalibank Limited
প্রিন্সিপাল অফিস, বরিশাল।
ফোন : ০৪৩১-৬৪৫১৫ ; ৬৪৮০৯; ৬৪৮৩৮
ই-মেইল: barisalpo@sonalibank.com.bd

শপথ নিলাম মুজিব বর্ষে
আমরা যাবো সবার শীর্ষে

D:\CHAND SULTANA\Internship.doc153

নং-পিওবি/প্রশাসন/এডিএম-০৫/ ১১৬৪

তারিখ : ১৮-০৩-২০২১

ম্যানেজার
সোনালী ব্যাংক লিমিটেড
চকবাজার শাখা
বরিশাল।

M. Zakir
22.03.2021

বিষয়ঃ ইন্টার্নশীপ সম্পন্ন করন প্রসঙ্গেঃ জনাব মোঃ শাফায়েত অর্খী, বিবিএ রোল নং- 16FIN068
ও (২) জনাব মোঃ জালাল উদ্দিন, বিবিএ রোল নং-16FIN026, ফিন্যান্স এন্ড ব্যাংকিং বিভাগ
বরিশাল বিশ্ববিদ্যালয়, বরিশাল।

জনাব,

উপর্যুক্ত বিষয়ে আপনাদের ০২/০১/২০২১ তারিখের চক/ইন্টার্নশীপ/পি-৩৮ ও পি-৩৯ সংখ্যক পত্রের সুপারিশ মোতাবেক উপরোল্লিখিত শিক্ষার্থীদের ইন্টার্নশীপ সম্পন্ন করন সংক্রান্ত মানব সম্পদ উন্নয়ন বিভাগ, সোনালী ব্যাংক লিমিটেড, প্রধান কার্যালয়, ঢাকার ০৮-০৩- ২০২১ তারিখের এইচ আর ডিডি/ইন্টার্নশীপ-১২৯/২০২১/৪৫৩ সংখ্যক পত্রের এক প্রস্ত ফটোকপি আপনাদের সদয় অবগতি ও প্রয়োজনীয় ব্যবস্থা গ্রহনের জন্য এতদসাথে প্রেরণ করা হলো।

উক্ত পত্রের শর্তমোতাবেক উল্লেখিত শিক্ষার্থীদের ইন্টার্নশীপ সম্পন্ন করার প্রয়োজনীয় ব্যবস্থা গ্রহনের জন্য অনুরোধ করা হলো।

সংযুক্তি : ০১ (এক) ।

আপনাদের বিশ্বস্ত,

(মাহবুবুল আলম)

এসিস্ট্যান্ট জেনারেল ম্যানেজার

Acknowledgement

At the very beginning, I would like to express my deep gratitude to Almighty Allah for blessing me with the ability, strength, and patience as well as guiding me to the right path, which helped me to complete my work timely and successfully. A single head can't thing a big deal. In this same manner I couldn't complete the report without the help of my surrounding people. I am indebted to a number of people who helped me a lot to complete my internship program and to prepare the report by their mental labor, kind advices, guidelines, suggestions, directions, and cooperation.

Firstly, I would like to pay my gratitude to my honorable supervisor ***Rabeya Sultana Lata, Assistant Professor, Department of Finance and Banking, University of Barishal.*** She was very kind to me through his guidance, thoughts, directions and time schedule.

I want to express my special thanks to Md. Abdul Mannan, Manager of Sonali Bank, Chawkbazar Branch, Barishal for appointing to accept me as an intern during the internship time. I am thankful to him.

In the end I would like to thank all the persons who have directly or indirectly contributed in preparing this report.

Executive Summary

Development! Digitalization!! Globalization!!! Is it possible without a strong financial intermediation? Without financial intermediation development, digitalization and globalization of country can't be thought. And banking sector helps a country to rebuild a enrich land. To ensure a global village, there are no alternative alike banks. Foreign trade signifies the globalization scenario. All most all of the foreign trades are organized by Banks. Like every commercial bank Sonali Bank Limited executes export, import operation not only in inside of country but also outside of country.

This report is based on foreign trade operations of Sonali Bank Limited. The Sonali Bank Limited makes a great contribution for the banking industry with full of ideal commercial activities through authentic performance. This report is prepared by analyzing last 5 years information of Sonali Bank Limited. As a leading commercial bank Sonali Bank operates it export & import business globally.

Basically this report highlights the crisis and prospectus of export, import business of Sonali Bank Limited.

Table of Content

Chapter No:	Topic Name	Page No:
	Letter of Transmittal	i
	Certificate of Supervisor	ii
	Letter of Acceptance	iii
	Acknowledgement	iv
	Executive Summary	v
Chapter:01	Introduction	1-4
	1.1 Background of the Study	2
	1.2 Objective of the Study	2
	1.3 Scope of the Study	2
	1.4 Limitation of the Study	3
	1.5 Methodology of the Study	3
	1.6 Source of Data	3
Chapter:02	Company Profile: Sonali Bank Limited	5-14
	2.1 History About Sonali Bank Limited	6
	2.2 Vision of Sonali Bank Limited	6
	2.3 Mission of Sonali Bank Limited	6
	2.4 Slogan of Sonali Bank Limited	6
	2.5 Objectives of the Bank	7
	2.6 Sonali Bank Limited Profile in a Nutshell	7
	2.7 Organizational Structure of Sonali Bank Ltd.	8
	2.8 Functional Hierarchy of SBL	9
	2.9 Products and Services of SBL	10
	2.10 International Banking of Sonali Bank Limited	12
	2.11 Oversea Bank	13
	2.11.1 Sonali Bank Limited Oversea Branches	13
	2.12 Brief Overview of Sonali Bank Limited, ChawkBazar Branch, Barishal	14
Chapter-03	Export & Import Operation of Sonali Bank Ltd.	15-20
	3.1 Foreign Trade	16
	3.1.1 Position of SBL in Foreign Trade	16
	3.2 Export	16
	3.2.1 Key Features of Export Function	16
	3.2.2 Export Management	17
	3.2.3 Export Activities by SBL	17
	3.3 Import	17
	3.3.1 Objectives of Import Trade	17
	3.3.2 Import Management	18
	3.3.3 Import Activities by SBL	18
	3.4 Essential Documents Related to Export Import Activities	18
	3.4.1 Letter of Credit (L/C)	19
	3.4.2 Bill of Exchange	20

Chapter No:	Topic Name		Page No:
	3.4.3	Bill of Lading	20
	3.4.4	Insurance Certificate	20
	3.4.5	Certificate of Origin	20
Chapter:04	Performance Evaluation of Export, Import Financing of Sonali Bank Ltd		21-31
	4.1	Foreign Trade (Export & Import) vs Sonali Bank Ltd.	22
	4.2	Export, Import Financing Activities by SBL	22
	4.3	Trend Analysis of Export in BD (2015-2019)	23
	4.4	Trend Analysis of Import in BD (2015-2019)	24
	4.5	Trend Analysis of Export in SBL (2015-2019)	25
	4.6	Trend Analysis of Import in SBL (2015-2019)	26
	4.7	Performance Evaluation of Export, Import Business among 3 Govt. Owned Banks	27
	4.8	SWOT Analysis of SBL (Especially on Foreign Trade)	30
Chapter:05	Internship Experience in Sonali Bank Ltd.		32-35
	5.1	Internship	33
	5.1.1	Internship in Bank	33
	5.1.2	Documents for Internship Application	33
	5.2	My Internship Experience in SBL, Chawkbazar Branch, Barishal	33
Chapter:06	Findings, Recommendations & Conclusion		36-39
	6.1	Findings	37
	6.2	Recommendations	38
	6.3	Conclusion	39
Chapter:07	References		40-41
	Appendix		42

Introduction

Now the era of business, we are living in a business planet. A single fault can destroy a complete business package. In the era of globalization and industrialization, we can't think without a financial institution like bank. Bank is the full and final destination for not only general people but also a businessman. In case of foreign trade (Export & Import), we can't think about without banking intermediation. Commercial banks play a dynamic role to enrich our economy. In foreign trade situation commercial bank creates an intermediation between exporters and importers. By this mechanism the concern parties (banks, exporters and importers) get benefited by commission, service charges, profit from exporting and profit from importing.

1.1 Background of the Study:

The internship report is prepared for the requirement of BBA program. The report is titled with "*Performance Evaluation of Export, Import Business of Sonali Bank Limited*". The students associated with this internship program are mandatory required to prepare a report. I have already finished my internship program and I have given my labor and experience for making this report. My labor, my perseverance will be treated fruitful, if the report meet up the objective of the journey.

1.2 Objective of the Study:

The major objective of this study is to make a clear analysis of Performance of export, import business of Sonali Bank Limited. The main objectives are mentioned bellow;

- ✓ To analyze the Foreign Trade activities of Sonali Bank Limited.
- ✓ To identify the export & import activities of Bangladesh.
- ✓ To identify the export & import activities of Sonali Bank LTD.

1.3 Scope of the Study:

This report is mainly performed for the analysis of export, import performance of Sonali Bank Ltd. The time duration is based on the last 5 calendar years. I have tried to display the overall foreign trade scenario, trend analysis and graphical representation about the concern variables efficiently. Findings and relevant recommendations are made based on that analysis. Due to branch privacy system I provide some relevant information from secondary sources.

1.4 Limitations of the Study:

In the world, none of us is fully perfect. Where in the paper work, obviously there has error, omission and lacking also. Although the study is mostly based on secondary sources, there is a possibility of manipulated data. I could not collect some information required at the time of the study. I have also faced the following disturbances while preparing this report;

- ✓ One and half months' (45 days) time is not enough for such an informative study. It is very difficult to acquire all the required information in such a short time.
- ✓ Due to COVID-19 Pandemic situation, physical communication with honorable supervisor and relevant person could not be easily executed.
- ✓ More analysis could not be executed due to privacy restriction from bank.
- ✓ Scarcity of records and related publications.
- ✓ Actual information could not be easily collected from the bank staffs due to their tight banking hours.
- ✓ Primary data could not be collected due to COVID-19 situation.
- ✓ Lack of previous internship experience.

1.5 Methodology of the Study:

This study is based on foreign trade of Sonali Bank Limited. Firstly I have tried to collect data from both primary and secondary sources. Data is evaluated from the annual report of Sonali Bank Limited during year 2015-2019 (last year report is not published yet). Although the study is based on secondary data, I have tried to find out some primary data from the clients and staffs of the bank. Secondly, I have displayed the overall foreign trade in Bangladesh and the performance of Sonali Bank Limited (SBL). By trend analyzing I have tried to show the overall picture of export, import business by BD other banks and SBL.

To compare with other banks performance I gave the proportional comparison among Sonali Bank Limited (SBL), Agrani Bank Limited (ABL) and Janata Bank Limited (JBL) during from 2015 to 2019.

Thirdly, for more clarification, I have given graphical representation of the analysis.

1.6 Sources of Data:

The information was collected properly to organize this report is both from primary and secondary sources.

Primary Sources of Data:

- ✓ Conversation with employees and officers of the banks.
- ✓ Conversation with the new and prospective clients.
- ✓ Initial observation of banking environment.

Secondary Sources of Data:

- ✓ Five years Annual Reports of Sonali Bank Ltd.
- ✓ Five years Annual Reports of Agrani Bank Limited (ABL), Janata Bank Limited (JBL) for proportional comparison.
- ✓ Data from web site of the Sonali Bank Ltd.
- ✓ Some reports and articles related to study
- ✓ Data from academic course.

2.1 About Sonali Bank Limited

Sonali Bank Limited is a state-owned leading commercial bank in Bangladesh. It is the largest bank of the country. Sonali Bank was established in 1972 under the Bangladesh Banks (Nationalization) Order, through the amalgamation and nationalization of the branches of National Bank of Pakistan, Bank of Bahawalpur and Premier Bank branches located in Pakistan until the 1971 Bangladesh Liberation War. When it was established, Sonali Bank had a paid up capital of 30 million taka. In 2001, it's authorized and paid up capital were Taka 10 billion and Taka 3.272 billion respectively. Presently, it's authorized and paid up capital is Taka 10 billion and Taka 9 billion respectively. The bank's reserve funds were Taka 60 million in 1979 and Taka 2.050 billion on 30 June 2000. The bank has been converted to a Public Limited Company with 100% ownership of the government and started functioning as Sonali Bank Limited from November 15, 2007 taking over all assets, liabilities and business of Sonali Bank. After corporatization, the management of the bank has been given required autonomy to make the bank competitive & to run its business effectively. The principal activities of the bank are providing all kinds of commercial banking services to the customers. It also performs Government Treasury functions as an agent of the Bangladesh Bank. The bank mainly handled the Export and Import Trade of Bangladesh with the socialist countries under various Barter Agreements.

2.2 Vision of Sonali Bank Limited:

Vision of the Sonali Bank LTD is Socially committed leading banking institution with global presence.

2.3 Mission of Sonali Bank Limited.

Dedicated to extend a whole range of quality production that support divergent needs of people aiming at enriching their lives, creating value for the stockholders and contributing toward socio-economic development of the country.

2.4 Slogan of Sonali Bank Limited:

“Your Trusted Partner in Innovative Banking” (*Sonali Bank, 2021*)

2.5 Objectives of the Bank:

The main objectives of the bank are to provide all type of banking products and services to the people. The bank participates in various socio-economic development activities and also takes part in implementation of various polities and program made by government. The key objectives of Sonali Bank Limited are given bellow;

- ✓ To collect of deposits
- ✓ To alleviate poverty
- ✓ To secure deposit
- ✓ To inspire savings
- ✓ To create employment
- ✓ To control loan
- ✓ To create medium of exchange
- ✓ To expand trade and commerce
- ✓ To assist Bangladesh Bank where Bangladesh Bank is absence

2.6 Sonali Bank Limited Profile in a Nutshell:

Sonali Bank Limited is a state-owned commercial bank in Bangladesh. It is the Largest Bank in the Country. A table is given below to see its profile at a glance;

Name of Company	Sonali Bank Limited
Chairman	Mr. Ziaul Hasan Siddiqui
CEO & Managing Director	Mr. Md. Ataur Rahman Prodhan
Legal Status	Public Limited Company
Date of Incorporation	June 03, 2007
Date of Vendor's Agreement	Nov 05, 2007
No of Branches	1227
Registered Office	35-42, 44 Motijheel Commercial Area, Bangladesh
Authorized Capital	BDT 6,000.00 Core
Paid –Up Capital	BDT 3,830.00 Core
Number of Employee	18,167
Phone-PABX	9550426-31,33,34, 9552924
FAX	88-02-9561410, 9552007
SWIFT	BSONBDDH
Web Site	http://:www.sonalibank.com.bd
Email	itd@sonalibank.com.bd

2.7 Organizational Structure of Sonali Bank Ltd.:

Figure: Organizational Structure of SBL

2.8 Functional Hierarchy of SBL:

Figure: Functional Hierarchy of SBL

2.9 Products and Services of SBL:

Core Business:

- ✓ Corporate Banking
- ✓ Project Finance
- ✓ SME Finance
- ✓ Remittance
- ✓ Trade Finance
- ✓ International Trade
- ✓ Lease Finance
- ✓ Consumer Credit
- ✓ Loan Syndication
- ✓ Foreign Exchange Dealing
- ✓ Investment
- ✓ Government Treasury Function
- ✓ Money Market Operation
- ✓ Rural and Micro credit
- ✓ Capital Market Operation.

Other Business:

- ✓ Government treasury bills
- ✓ Locker Service
- ✓ A.T.M card
- ✓ Utility Bills Collections
- ✓ Ancillary Services

Islamic Banking Services:

Deposit Products:

- ✓ Al-Wadeeah Current Account (AWCA)
- ✓ Mudaraba Savings Account (MSA)
- ✓ Mudaraba Special Notice Deposit Account (MSNDA)
- ✓ Mudaraba Term Deposit Account (MTDA)
- ✓ Mudaraba Hajj Saving Account (MHSA)
- ✓ Mudaraba Sonali Monthly Deposit Scheme (SMDS)
- ✓ Mudaraba Monthly Profit Scheme (MMPS).

Investment Product:

- ✓ Bai-Murabaha
- ✓ Bai-Muajjal
- ✓ Bai-Salam
- ✓ Bai-Istisna.

Other Services:

Sonali Bank Limited introduces multiple special services with its network of branches throughout the country in addition to its normal banking operations.

Collection:

- ✓ Gas bills
- ✓ Electricity bills
- ✓ Telephone bills
- ✓ Water/Sewerage bills
- ✓ Municipal holding Tax
- ✓ Passport fees, visa fees and Travel tax
- ✓ Customs & Excise duties
- ✓ Source tax and VAT
- ✓ Jakat fund
- ✓ Hajj deposit

Payments:

- ✓ Pension of employees of government and other corporate bodies
- ✓ Bangladesh bank employees" pension
- ✓ Army pension
- ✓ British pension
- ✓ Student's stipend/ scholarship
- ✓ Government and non-government teacher's salary
- ✓ Food procurement bill on behalf of government.

Social Welfare Services:

- ✓ Old age allowance
- ✓ Widows, divorces and destitute women allowance
- ✓ Freedom fighter allowance
- ✓ Rehabilitation allowance for acid survival women
- ✓ Maternal allowances for poor women

2.10 International Banking of Sonali Bank Limited:

Sonali Bank Limited expertise in International Banking has a record of in-house growth over more than half a century. Its pioneer role in handling foreign trade and foreign exchange transactions ever independence of the country still remains unchallenged. With wide network of branches at home and also a large number of correspondent banks worldwide it is singularly handling the largest volume of export-import business including home-bound remittances.

Products & Services:

- ✓ Export Credit (Pre-shipment & Post shipment)
- ✓ Facilitating Supplier's Credit
- ✓ LCs (Letters of Credit)
- ✓ *Guarantees in Foreign Currency:*
 - Bid Bond
 - Performance Guarante
 - Advance Payment Guarantee.
- ✓ Bill Purchasing/Discounting
- ✓ Remittance, collection, purchases & sales of Foreign Currency & Traveller's Cheques.
- ✓ NRAT (Non-Resident Account in Taka)
- ✓ NFCD A/c (Non-Resident Foreign Currency Deposit)
- ✓ RFCD A/c (Resident Foreign Currency Deposit)
- ✓ Convertible and Non-convertible Taka Account
- ✓ Forward contracts
- ✓ Correspondent Banking Relations

Import Finance:

Sonali Bank Limited supports its customers by providing facilities throughout the import process to ensure smooth running of their business. The facilities are:

- ✓ Import Letter of Credit.
- ✓ Post Import Financing (LIM,LTR etc).
- ✓ Import collection services & Shipping Guarantees.

Export Finance:

Sonali Bank Limited offers extra cover to its customers for whole export process to speed up receipt of proceeds. The facilities are:

- a. Export Letters of Credit advising.
- b. Pre-shipment Export Financing.
- c. Export documents negotiation.
- d. Letter of Credit confirmation.

2.11 Oversea Bank:

Corporations and individuals bank overseas for many reasons. There are the issues of security, doing business in privacy, gaining more access to foreign markets, facilitating international customers, traders and business partners and capitalizing on advanced banking facilities and services. Most of these aims are possible because overseas banks offshore are specially designed to operate on an international scale given the fact that their primary purpose is to serve corporations and individuals are non-residents of the jurisdiction under which they operate. Overseas banks offshore must be licensed in order to operate and are regulated by both domestic and international banking laws. In order to be licensed, offshore banks must first meet specific standards that are established with regard to capital and shareholder requirements, directorship, banking business and operations conducted, management, presence in the jurisdiction, quality of staff, track record and overall competence of the institution in being able to provide overseas banking services.

2.11.1 Sonali Bank Limited Oversea Branches:

United States:

There are currently four in US in Washington DC, New York, Chicago, Los Angeles

United Kingdom:

There are four branches in the UK, one located in Osborn Street, in London another in Small Heath; brimingham and in Manchester

India:

There are two branches in India one in Kolkata Branch and other in Siliguri Branch

Profile of SBL in Kolkata

CEO & Deputy General Manager	Mrs. Rawshan Jahan
Branch	Sonali Bank Limited Kolkata Branch
Location	'Wachel Molla Mansion' 1st Floor 8, Lenin Sarani (Dharmatala Street) Kolkata - 700 013 West Bengal, India
Phone	Phone: 00-91-33-2228-2255/56(PABX) 00-91-33-2228-2254(CEO & DGM)
Cell	00-91-9830024868 (CEO & DGM)
Fax	0091-33-2228-2258
SWIFT	BSONINCC
Website	www.sonalibank.in

2.12 Brief Overview of Sonali Bank Limited, ChawkBazar Branch, Barishal:

I have already finished my internship from this branch. The overview of this bank is given below;

Bank Name	Sonali Bank Limited
Branch name	Chawkbazar Branch, Barishal
Location	Chawk Bazar, Girza Moholla Road, Barishal
District	Barishal
Branch Code	070
SWIFT Code	BSONBDH
Routing Number	200060703
Service Hours	Sunday: 10.00 AM-4.00 PM Monday: 10.00 AM-4.00 PM Tuesday: 10.00 AM-4.00 PM Wednesday: 10.00 AM-4.00 PM Thursday: 10.00 AM-4.00 PM Friday: Closed Saturday: Closed
Working Day	Sunday-Thursday (Except Holiday)
E-Mail	brchawkbazar@sonalibank.com.bd
Telephone	043152536

Chapter:03

Export & Import Operation of
Sonali Bank Ltd.

3.1 Foreign Trade

Trading between one country to country is called foreign trade. Foreign trade plays a vital role in the economic development of country. Foreign trade is a mechanism for gaining productive efficiency. Basically foreign trade deals with export and import activities.

3.1.1 Position of SBL in Foreign Trade

Foreign trade business is totally controlled by the Bangladesh Bank. Central Bank permits some specific branches to perform the foreign trade. Those who have the authority to operate foreign trade business are known as Authorized Dealer (AD) branch. SBL is an Authorized Dealer (AD) Bank. SBL operates foreign exchange trade through its branches. To handle foreign business effectively and efficiently, the SBL has developed a wide network of correspondents throughout the world. The Bank has more than 600 foreign correspondents all over the world

3.2 Export

Simply, a product or service is sold out abroad that can be called Export. Exports are products and services that are produced in parent country, but then sold to customer outside the country (abroad). By exporting inflow of fund is increasing from foreign buyers. Like main exporter, bank can gain profit through assisting exporter.

3.2.1 Key features of export function

Export function is used to measure export.

Enriching selling of product to countries which need such goods.

Enhancing marketplace for goods.

Gaining profit through exports.

Assisting a rustic increase the value.

3.2.2 Export Management

Export management is a system of planning, organizing, co-coordinating and control export strategy or activities to gain desired export goal efficiently with consecutively. It is basically related to activities and type of management that brings incorporation of an export business. It is the use of managerial process to the serviceable area of exports.

3.2.3 Export Activities by SBL

- i. Export guarantees
- ii. Advising/confirming letters – letters of credit
- iii. Advance for deferred payments exports
- iv. Pre-shipment advances
- v. Purchase of foreign bills
- vi. Negotiations of foreign bills
- vii. Advance against bills for collection

3.3 Import

Bringing goods or services into a country from another country for sale is called **Import**. An import is a product or service produced abroad and purchase home country. Imported goods or services are becoming more attractive due scare domestic goods and services as well as quality of product and service also.

3.3.1 Objectives of import trade

The import trade is referred to goods and services purchased into one nation from another. Imports are the backbone of the international trade. As middle developing country (in accordance with United Nation, 2021) Bangladesh tries to minimize importing. But to keep pace with the running world, there is not enough alternative option for Bangladesh. The most imported goods are electronic products, vehicle, motor parts, weapons etc.

The key objectives of import trade are given bellow;

To boost up industrialization

- ✓ Developing countries import scarce raw materials, capital goods and advanced technology required for rapid industrial development.

To full fill up local demand

- ✓ The goods which are in demand but are not available in the country are imported.

To cope up with natural hazard

- ✓ During drought, flood, earthquake and other natural calamities country import food grains and other essential commodities to prevent starvation.

To enrich outstanding living

- ✓ Imports enable consumers in the home country to enjoy a wide variety of products of high quality.
- ✓ It helps in improving the standard of living of masses.

To signify national defense

- ✓ The importer must get the receipt of credit from his concerned bank and send it to the foreign supplier.

3.3.2 Import Management

Import management refers assessment of market, financial matter, execution and making suitable pre/post activities associated with import. The procedure for import trade differs from country to country, depending upon the import policies, the statutory requirements and customs of different countries. In all most all the countries of the world import trade is controlled and managed by government. Simply, the procedure of import processing is called import management.

3.3.3 Import Activities by SBL

- i. Letter of credit (LC)
- ii. Advance bills
- iii. Bills for collection
- iv. Import loans and guarantees

3.4 Essential documents related to export import activities

In foreign exchange activities Bank mostly provides Export and Import facilities. For performing foreign exchange activities in a bank we require certain documents. Documents used in exports and imports are given bellow

3.4.1 Letter of Credit (L/C)

Letter of credit is the most popular mechanism of foreign trade. A letter of credit is a definite undertaking of the issuing Bank to make payment to the exporter on behalf of the importer. Here, the banker works on behalf of importer. Basically, it is document that guarantees the buyer's payment to the sellers. It is issued by a bank and ensures the timely and full payment to the seller. If the buyer is unable to make such a payment, the bank covers the full or the remaining amount on behalf the buyer (importer).

Types of L/C:

Letters of Credit are classified into various types according to the method of settlement employed. All credits must clearly indicate in major categories.

- ❖ Negotiation credit
- ❖ Red clause credit
- ❖ Revolving credit
- ❖ Sight payment credit
- ❖ Deferred payment credit
- ❖ Stand-by credit
- ❖ Transferable credit
- ❖ Back to back credit
- ❖ Acceptance credit

Parties of L/C:

Various parties are involved in LC mechanism. Those are briefly explained below;

- i. Opening Bank:**
The opening Bank is one that issues the letter of credit at the request of the buyer.
- ii. Advising Bank:**
It is the Bank through which the L/C is advised to the exporters. This Bank is actually situated in exporter's country
- iii. Paying Bank:**
The paying Bank only pays the drafts drawn under the credit.
- iv. Negotiating Bank:**
It is the Bank, which negotiates the bill and pays the amount of the beneficiary. The advising Bank and the negotiating Bank may or may not be the same.

v. Confirming Bank:

It is the Bank, which adds its confirmation to the credit and it is done at the request of issuing Bank. Confirming Bank may or may not be advising Bank.

3.4.2 Bill of Exchange:

The bill of exchange is the instrument that is mostly used in both internal and international trade. The payment for the goods is received by the seller through the medium of a bill of exchange drawn on the buyer for the amount depending on the contract. It is a negotiable instrument.

3.4.3 Bill of Lading:

A bill of lading is a document which is usually stipulated in a credit when the products are dispatched by sea. It is an evidence of agreement of carriage, is a receipt for the products, and is a document of title to the products. It concludes a paper which is needed to vindicate insurance claim.

3.4.4 Insurance Certificate:

Insurance is a contractual agreement between insurer and insure. The document which provides the insurance agreement can be referred as insurance certificate. Theoretically, insurance refers to a contractual arrangement in which one party, i.e. insurance company or the insurer agrees to compensate the loss or damage sustained to another party. In foreign trade scenario insurance certificate is most important thing that enlightens foreign business.

3.4.5 Certificate of Origin:

This is a certificate issued by a recognized authority in exporting country certifying the country of origin of the goods.

Chapter: 04

Performance Evaluation of
Export, Import Financing of
Sonali Bank Ltd

4.1 Foreign Trade (Export & Import) vs Sonali Bank Ltd.

A number of commercial banks in Bangladesh are engaged with foreign trade. We know Sonali Bank is the largest state owned bank of Bangladesh sometimes acting as Bangladesh Bank also. There is a significant impact of foreign trade strategy by SBL. In case of foreign business, it has strong line up both country side and abroad than other state owned bank.

4.2 Export, Import Financing Activities by SBL

Sonali Bank's expertise in International Banking has a record of in-house growth over more than half a century. Its pioneer role in handling foreign trade ever before independence of the country still remains unchallenged. In foreign trade phenomena SBL contributes itself than other state owned bank in Bangladesh. In case of export business finance is perceived as one of the important elements. Sonali Bank assists both exporter and importer. Sonali bank as a commercial bank provides certain facilities to the exporters to boost up export earnings.

The traditional & non-traditional sectors in which Sonali Bank provides export-financing facilities are as follows:

- RDM (Ready Made Garments) in all sorts.
- Jute manufactures
- Jute – raw & meshta
- Fish & Prawns.
- Hides, Skins & Leather.
- Tea etc

Sonali Bank is the major financier of import business in our country. Sonali Bank helps the importer in many foreign trading tools. In extend credit, grant and other facilities Sonali Bank finance to the following sectors:

- Chemicals
- Iron & steels
- Cereal & cereal preparations
- Dairy products & eggs
- Machinery & transport equipment.
- Petroleum & petroleum products
- Textile, yarn, fabrics, article & related products
- Other including loans & grants.

4.3 Trend Analysis of Export in BD (2015-2019)

Trend analysis is the system of evaluating and predicting tentative variable from year to year. In this section I would show the overall export scenario of Bangladesh during last 5 years (2015-2019).

Figure 1: Export by BD (2015-2019)

Source: World Bank

Interpretation:

This line chart (Figure-1) shows the graphical representation of export scenario during year 2015-2019. There is an upward trending among those years. Moreover, I try to show export tendency of COVID-19 situation. Here, export falls significantly (46.36 to 33.36 Billion US\$) in 2020 (up to July) due to COVID-19. COVID-19 harms export progress tremendously.

4.4 Trend Analysis of Import in BD (2015-2019)

In this section I try to display Bangladesh Import scenario during year 2015-2019.

Figure 2: Import by BD (2015-2019)

Source: World Bank

Interpretation:

This line chart illustrates graphical representation of import situation by Bangladesh. There is a fluctuation in 2015 to 2019. In 2019 import was reached a high of (64.86 Billion US\$). Basically I show 5 years trend analysis. But today we are living in COVID situation. COVID-19 has taught a good lesson to the banking sector especially foreign trade. Here, in 2020 (July) import was dripped by 46.24 billion US\$. What is the reason behind this scenario? Well, In COVID-19 all most all of the countries had suffered for lockdown and so shipment process had stopped. For this reasons import was dropped dramatically in 2020.

4.5 Trend Analysis of Export in SBL (2015-2019)

Export Business of Sonali Bank Limited (2015-2019)

Year	Export by SBL (BDT in Crore)	Δ%
2014	10,192.25	
2015	10,596.62	+3.97%
2016	11,332.83	+6.95%
2017	12,021.34	+6.08%
2018	12,134.45	+0.94%
2019	12,240.27	+0.87%

Graph

Figure 3: Growth of Export Business by SBL (2015-2019)

Interpretation:

This line chart illustrates the percentage of growth of export business by Sonali Bank Ltd. from 2015 to 2019. In 2016 export business by SBL was reached a high of percentage. In 2017 it was slightly dropped. Finally in 2018 & 2019 the export business by SBL came down rapidly. This might be happened due to any banking environmental fluctuation between bank and importers.

4.6 Trend Analysis of Import in SBL (2015-2019)

Sonali Bank assist importer by opening LC and funding also. Here I try to describe import business by Sonali Bank during year 2015 to 2019.

Year	Import by SBL (BDT in Crore)	$\Delta\%$
2014	902.72	
2015	941.64	+4.31%
2016	1,094.81	+16.26%
2017	1,723.95	+57.47%
2018	2,508.31	+45.49%
2019	3,054.50	+21.77%

Graph

Figure 4: Growth of Import Business by SBL (2015-2019)

Interpretation:

This line chart illustrates the picture of import business situation from 2015 to 2019 of Sonali Bank Ltd. Import position was upward trend from 2015 to 2017. But from 2017 to 2019 it was decreased significantly. In 2017 it was reached high position.

4.7 Performance evaluation of export, import business among 3 Govt. owned Banks

Performance evaluation of export, import business among 3 Govt. owned Bank in Bangladesh

Export Situation:

In this section I try to show the financial performance of export, import business of Sonali Bank Limited(SBL), Agrani Bank Limited(ABL) and Janata Bank Limited (JBL) during last 5 years (2015-2019)

Year	SBL	ABL	JBL	Total(SBL+ABL+JBL)	SBL of 100%	ABL of 100%	JBL of 100%	Total %
2015	10597	7543	14537.36	32676.98	32.42839455	23.08352853	44.48807693	100
2016	11333	7396	15445.42	34174.25	33.16189821	21.64202579	45.19607599	100
2017	12021	7059	13992.09	33072.43	36.34852353	21.34406211	42.30741436	100
2018	12134	8280	11468.1	31882.55	38.05984779	25.97031919	35.96983303	100
2019	12240	10872.9	9739.82	32852.99	37.2577047	33.09561778	29.64667752	100
Total	58326	41150.9	65182.79	164659.2				
Overall %	35.422	24.99156	39.586485	100				

Amount: BDT in Crore

Figure 5: Export Business by SBL, ABL, JBL (2015-2019)

Sources: Annual Report of Selected Bank

Interpretation:

This column chart (figure 5) illustrates the graphical representation of export situation of SBL, ABL and JBL from 2015-2019. From 2015-2017, JBL performed well than SBL and ABL. ABL performed worse from 2015-2017. From 2018-2019, SBL performed better than ABL and JBL. From 2015-2018 ABL performance was not satisfactory enough. JBL performed bad in 2019 among last five years. Overall JBL performance is good enough than SBL and ABL.

Remarks:

Position in Export Business	Bank Name
1 st	Janata Bank Limited (JBL)
2 nd	Sonali Bank Limited (SBL)
3 rd	Agrani Bank Limited (ABL)

Import Situation:

Import Business Analysis among SBL, ABL & JBL during 2015-2019

Year	SBL	ABL	JBL	SBL+ABL+JBL	SBL @100%	ABL @100%	JBL @100%	Total %
2015	941.64	10917	14718.18	26576.82	3.5430	41.0771	55.3797	100%
2016	1094.81	10153	12665	23912.81	4.5783	42.4584	52.9632	100%
2017	1723.95	13267	14358.22	29359.17	5.8739	45.2040	48.9220	100%
2018	2508.31	23551	22041.37	48100.64	5.2147	48.9618	45.8234	100%
2019	3045.21	38841	21095	62981.5	4.8355	61.6704	33.4938	100%
Total	9314.21	96729	84877.77	190920.98	4.878568	50.66442	44.45702	100%
Overall %	4.878568	50.66442	44.45702	100				

Amount: BDT in Crore

Figure 6: Import Business by SBL, ABL, JBL (2015-2019)

Interpretation: From 2015 to 2017 JBL took the first position and SBL took the last position in import business. But the following two years (2018 and 2019) ABL reached at high and SBL took the last position. Overall ABL performed better among three during last five years.

Remarks:

Position in Import Business	Bank Name
1st	Agrani Bank Limited (ABL)
2nd	Janata Bank Limited (JBL)
3rd	Sonali Bank Limited (SBL)

4.8 SWOT Analysis of SBL (Especially on Foreign Trade)

SWOT stands for strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in a certain situation. Here, strengths and weaknesses are assigned as internal factors. Then opportunities and threats are treated as external factors. I briefly discuss about SWOT indicators perception from foreign trade (Export & Import).

Strengths

- ✓ Bank has a very competent and experienced top Management.
- ✓ SBL is operating their business all over the country with 1186 branches.
- ✓ Strong network with other commercial bank.
- ✓ Indirect direction is gained by Central Bank.
- ✓ The largest govt. owned bank.
- ✓ Strong communication with LIBOR and DIBOR.

Weakness

- ✓ Poor marketing policy. This is why the bank can't attract both exporters and importer properly.
- ✓ More traditional mechanism.
- ✓ Scarcity of ATM services. For this, the small export, import group can't get current services.
- ✓ More complex transaction system than export, import Bank.

Opportunities

- ✓ Due to state owned bank, it can improve marketing policies.
- ✓ It can attract foreign group by helping through funding.
- ✓ It can improve e-banking.
- ✓ Growing need for alternate banking channel
- ✓ Banks can offer new innovative products services to the exporters and importers.

Threats

- ✓ A number of competitor banks which are working for foreign trade efficiently.
- ✓ Many exporters trust to multinational bank rather than local commercial bank like SBL.
- ✓ Latest generation private commercial banks offer attractive products and services to foreign traders than state own bank.
- ✓ Scarcity of market information that suffers the foreign traders.
- ✓ Huge digital corruption in Sonali Bank Ltd.
- ✓ Poor monitoring. This is why there is a huge chance of default loan and fake L/C mechanism.

Chapter: 05
Internship Experiences in
Sonali Bank Ltd

Internship Experience in Sonali Bank Ltd.

5.1 Internship:

Simply, Internship refers the position of a student or trainee who works in an organization with pay or without pay, in order to gain work experience or satisfy requirements for a qualification.

5.1.1 Internship in Bank:

Internship in a bank is wide spread method of learning practical knowledge that has already achieved in academic program. The students of BBA Program background, especially Finance & Banking gain practical knowledge in banking sectors. In the internship, the trainee assists full-time/part time with Analysts and Associates with everything imaginable, ranging from menial tasks such as presentations, financial modeling, and deal analysis.

5.1.2 Documents for Internship Application:

Application deadlines may be early for some internship, and the process might require some time to get everything out before the deadline. But the whole process of applying for internship differs organization to organization. Organizations may require the following papers & tools;

- ✓ formal application,
- ✓ forwarding letter from running institution,
- ✓ resume,
- ✓ cover letter,
- ✓ transcripts,
- ✓ recent photos of trainee,
- ✓ two or three letters of recommendation(if need),
- ✓ as well as an essay on why you're interested in interning for the company or some other related question.

Not all internships have the same requirements.

5.2 My Internship Experience in SBL,Chawkbazar Branch, Barishal:

Internship is a practical field work for every trainee. In 1st February, 2021 I joined Sonali Bank Limited, Chawk Bazar Branch, Barishal. Like every trainee I have also learnt from this bank management.. But, due to COVID-19 situation & limited duration of internship I can't

learn more. However, I have already gathered some experiences that might not possible to learn in academic phenomena. My experiences are briefly explained below;

✓ **Communication Experience:**

From internship application to the end I have developed my communication skill. The honorable manager of the bank is so friendly and a man of well manner.

✓ **Leadership Experience:**

Theoretically, we students of BBA background (Finance & Banking) know about leadership, the quality of leaders. But we had fewer opportunities to get practical touch of leaders. Here, I learn a lot from the banks management. I have noticed the direction from upper level management to lower level management. I also noticed the chain of command in an organization.

✓ **Clients Management:** In this situation, I have learnt a lot from client's management. Here, I have learnt, how to deal with clients, how to convince clients, how to manage clients and how to give the information to the clients.

✓ **Experiences from Basic Operations of Bank:** Due to pandemic situation I didn't learn a lots. But the things I have learnt that is impossible to learn in academic modules.

I have gained some experiences associated with basic operations of bank (especially Sonali Bank Limited) that are given below;

- Opening bank account
- Issuing check
- Bill payments collection
- Govt. service charge collection (Chalan/Voucher)
- Co-operating with cash officer

✓ **Technical Experiences:**

As a trainee there is a less scope of using technological tools associated with banking activities. I have gotten a little concept of technical tools about;

- Real time website linking with various branches.
- Basic operation of currency counting machine.

This internship is the fruitful internship for my academic life. I should have known more. But due to tight time management in internship period & COVID-19 situation I couldn't learn as I desired. However, I believe that those described experiences hopefully give me a golden career in near future.

Chapter: 06

Findings, Recommendations
& Conclusion

6.1 Findings

It is very hard to find out the tentative scenario within a single study. However, I try to display the export, import business performance of Sonali Bank Limited by preparing this report.

The findings that I obtained from the report on export, import business of Sonali Bank are follows:

- ✓ In Bangladesh, export was decreased significantly (46.36 to 33.36 Billion US\$) in 2020 (up to July) due to COVID-19. COVID-19 harms export progress tremendously. Sonali Bank also suffers for it.
- ✓ There was a fluctuation in 2015 to 2019. In 2019 import was reached a high of (64.86 Billion US\$) in Bangladesh. In 2020 (July) import was dripped by 46.24 billion US\$. Sonali Bank Limited was influenced by this deduction also.
- ✓ Growth rate of export business of Sonali Bank Limited is not so good. In 2017 it was slightly dropped. Finally in 2018 & 2019 the export business by SBL came down rapidly.
- ✓ Import position of Sonali Bank Limited was upward trend from 2015 to 2017. But from 2017 to 2019 it was decreased significantly. In 2017 it was reached high position.
- ✓ **In export business**, Janata Bank Limited (JBL) performed well than Sonali Bank Limited (SBL) and Agrani Bank Limited (ABL) From 2015-2017. ABL performed worse from 2015-2017. From 2018-2019, SBL performed better than ABL and JBL. From 2015-2018 ABL performance was not satisfactory enough. JBL performed bad in 2019 among last five years.
- ✓ **In import business**, : From 2015 to 2017 JBL took the first position and SBL took the last position in import business. But the following two years (2018 and 2019) ABL reached at high and SBL took the last position.
- ✓ **In export business**, SBL performrd marginally during last five years.
- ✓ **In import business**, SBL performed very bad.
- ✓ SBL has performed in complex transaction system than export, import Bank.

6.2 Recommendations

It is very difficult to suggest something to Sonali Bank Limited. In this study I have already found out some crisis and prospectus of Sonali Bank Limited in foreign trade. My recommendations are as follows;

- ✓ Sonali Bank Limited (SBL) should develop sectors wise export-financing facilities.
- ✓ SBL should practice the most popular and worldwide products and services related to export and import business.
- ✓ Letter of Credit (L/C) opening system for the importer should be easier as export-import bank.
- ✓ To avoid fraudulent and misstatement SBL should use modern technology.
- ✓ Punishment & reward system should be applied to the exporters and importers. That can be brought a balance foreign trade by SBL.
- ✓ Export & import business of SBL is not good enough. Specially, import business was so bad in last 5 years.
- ✓ To make a good foreign trade, SBL should attract the exporter & importers by practicing; funding, charging less charge initially.
- ✓ To protect digital theft SBL should upgrade security pace, fixing bug in real time operating system also.
- ✓ Strong justification of LC mechanism should be updated. By opening fake LC a large amount of money is embezzled. SBL should take hard action against money laundering.

6.3 Conclusion

We are living in a banking environment. Bank is interrelated to our daily life. The people associated with foreign trade can't think a single transaction without banking activities. I have already completed my internship from Sonali Bank Limited. And this study is based on export, import business by Sonali Bank Limited. Sonali Bank Limited is the largest state owned commercial bank in Bangladesh. As a commercial bank it has great impact on export, import business in Bangladesh. But analyzing all types of relevant data it is said that financial health of export, import business of SBL is not so good. As a leading govt. owned commercial bank it should have strong lineup in export, import business. But, unfortunately the bank could not cope up with the competitive bank like, Agrani Bank Limited, Janata Bank Limited and other export-import bank in Bangladesh.

Sonali Bank Limited is the leading bank in our country. It has the largest number of branches in Bangladesh. It has a large volume of manpower also. In simple word, it has the capacity of dominating the foreign trade business. If SBL uses its resources in an effective and efficient way, it will be a pioneer export-import bank in near future.

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Appendix

Abbreviation

<i>SBL</i>	<i>Sonali Bank Limited</i>
<i>ABL</i>	<i>Agrani Bank Limited</i>
<i>JBL</i>	<i>Janata Bank Limited</i>
<i>BB</i>	<i>Bangladesh Bank</i>
<i>WB</i>	<i>World Bank</i>
<i>BBS</i>	<i>Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics</i>
<i>L/C</i>	<i>Letter of Credit</i>
<i>DD</i>	<i>Demand Draft</i>
<i>SWIFT</i>	<i>Society for Worldwide Interbank Telecommunication</i>
<i>RDM</i>	<i>Ready Made Garments</i>
<i>AD</i>	<i>Authorized Dealers</i>

4.5 Trend Analysis of Export in SBL (2015-2019)

Year	Export by SBL (BDT in Crore)	Δ	Δ%
2014	10,192.25		
2015	10,596.62	404.37	3.96743
2016	11,332.83	736.21	6.94759
2017	12,021.34	688.51	6.07536
2018	12,134.45	113.11	0.94091
2019	12,240.27	105.82	0.87206

4.6 Trend Analysis of Import in SBL (2015-2019)

Year	Import by SBL (BDT in Crore)	Δ	Δ%
2014	902.72		
2015	941.64	38.92	4.31141
2016	1,094.81	153.17	16.2663
2017	1,723.95	629.14	57.4657
2018	2,508.31	784.36	45.4978
2019	3,054.50	546.19	21.7752